

Internet Addiction among Students: Study from a Medical College, Adilabad.**Omprakash Lolam¹, Moluguru Pradeep², Raghunath Miryala³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Adilabad, Telangana, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Adilabad, Telangana, India³Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Adilabad, Telangana, India

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Abstract**Introduction:** Usage of internet has increased drastically over the past few years and excessive use has negative health consequences posing a serious public health concern. Present study was undertaken with an objective to determine the internet addiction among students from a teaching medical college.**Material & Methods:** It was a cross sectional study done among 550 Undergraduate Medical students, Post graduates, BSC and allied science students. Internet Addiction Test (IAT) tool was used to assess the internet addiction. Students were explained about purpose of study and confidentiality of information was ensured.**Results:** Mean age of the respondents was 21.42 years with female preponderance (74.4%). In undergraduate and post graduate medical students, majority of them had mild and moderate addiction compared to BSC and allied science students. Among MBBS students, highest mean IAT score was found in 3rd year (44.47) followed by Internship & 4th year. No significant difference was observed in mean IAT score among post graduates. Among BSC students, 2nd and 3rd year students had higher mean IAT scores which was statistically significant ($p=0.04$). With regards to symptoms in specific, excessive use, neglect work, lack of control and neglect social life were statistically significant with category of students.**Conclusions:** High prevalence of Internet addiction was found in the present study across all the four categories of students included. A multidisciplinary approach involving students, parents, college faculty, psychiatrists, psychologist and stakeholder's opinions and suggestions needs to be considered to tackle this global public health issue and to reduce its impact.**Keywords:** Internet, Students, Addiction, Internet Addiction Test.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

In the current digital era of technology and information, Internet usage has become ubiquitous. Internet is being used for various aspects such as to get information, online learning, social media and many more. Internet is crucial in this digital era but its usage is like a two edged sword which needs to be carefully monitored or else it can lead to addiction. Usage of internet has increased drastically over the past few years and this increase has definite benefits for the users but excessive use has negative health consequences posing a serious public health concern. Though internet addiction is not recognized in the World Health Organization's (WHO) International Classification of Diseases 11th revision (ICD-11), gaming disorders which includes internet usage appears in the ICD-11. [1,2]

Internet usage among students is also increasing everyday wherein students use internet for academic purpose such as need for online resources, updating their knowledge, preparation for future entrance exams. But along with academic purposes, students use internet also for social media platforms, watching movies & short videos, playing online games etc. Internet addiction has many consequences impacting their health, academic performance, professional development. Impact of health not just limited to physical aspects (sedentary lifestyle, eye related issues) but also on mental dimensions (loss of sleep, stress, depression, social isolation). [3,4]

Over the past decades, a number of instruments or tools have been developed for screening and diagnose Internet addiction including the Internet

Addiction Test (IAT), the compulsive internet use scale, the internet related addictive behavior inventory, the internet consequences scales, and few more. [5,6] But among all the above instruments, the most widely used is the Internet Addiction Test (IAT) proposed by Kimberly S.Young (1998) and it exhibits good internal reliability and validity. [7,8]

Recognizing the importance of the topic, the present study was undertaken with an objective to determine the internet addiction among students from a teaching medical college. Students represents the young population and the findings of the study may provide us an insight about the magnitude of the problem and help us to find the ways to tackle them and take appropriate measures to reduce the impact of internet addiction.

Material & Methods

Present study was a cross sectional study done in the Department of Psychiatry, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Adilabad, Telangana. Study duration was from June 2023 to September 2023.

Sample size was estimated by considering the prevalence of mild internet addiction of 54.6% from a previous study (Abbas et al) [9], with an allowable error of 8% of P and 95% level of confidence. Upon substitution, sample size came to 519 which were rounded off into 550. Hence the final sample size was 550. Undergraduate Medical students, Post graduate medical students, BSC and allied science students included in the study and they were selected using simple random sampling using random number tables.

Internet Addiction Test (IAT) tool was used to assess the internet addiction. IAT is a 20-item scale

that measures the presence and severity of internet addiction. Each question has a five point Likert scale from 0 to 5 where 0 meant not applicable to 5 meant always. Higher the score higher is the severity of internet addiction with points 0 to 30 considered to be normal level of internet usage, 31 to 49 mild level of internet addiction, 50 to 79 moderate level and scores of 80 to 100 indicate a severe dependency on Internet.

Students were explained about the purpose of the study and confidentiality of information was ensured. Informed consent was taken from the students prior to the start of the study and those who didn't give consent were excluded from the study.

Data entry was done using Microsoft Excel 2019 version and analysis using EPI INFO version 7. Categorical data was presented in percentages and numerical data using mean and standard deviation. ANOVA test was used to determine the association with p value less than 0.05 considered to be statistically significant.

Results

Total 550 students were included in the study including 274 MBBS students, Interns 56, Post graduate medical students 47, BSC nursing 157 and BSC allied sciences students 16. Mean age of the respondents was 21.42 years with minimum age being 18 years and maximum 39 years. Gender distribution showed female preponderance with almost three fourth being females (74.4%). All (n=550) mentioned that they use Internet for work. With regards to years of online internet usage, mean years of usage was 4.74 years.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

	Number	Percentage
Age (Mean in years)	21.42±2.78	
Gender		
Male	141	25.6%
Female	409	74.4%
Course & Year		
MBBS		
I	46	8.4%
II	72	13.1%
III	73	13.3%
IV	83	15.1%
Internship	56	10.2%
Post Graduate		
I	22	4%
II	17	3.1%
III	08	1.4%
BSC		
I	46	8.3%
II	48	8.7%
III	34	6.2%
IV	29	5.3%
Allied Science	16	2.9%

Table 2: Categorization of IAT score

Category of Students	IAT Score severity				Total
	No addiction	Mild	Moderate	Severe	
MBBS students & Internees	92 (27.9%)	149 (45.1%)	86 (26.1%)	03 (0.9%)	330
Post Graduate students	11 (23.4%)	24 (51.1%)	12 (25.5%)	--	47
BSC students	93 (59.3%)	50 (31.8%)	14 (8.9%)	--	157
Allied science students	05 (31.2%)	06 (37.6%)	05 (31.2%)	--	16

Chi-square value=54.88 P=0.00001 (Statistically significant)

With regards to severity of IAT score, categorization into mild, moderate and severe was done and comparison was done between IAT score severity and category of students. In undergraduate and post graduate medical students, majority of them had mild and moderate addiction compared to BSC and allied science students. The association between IAT score severity and category of students was found to be statistically significant in

chi square test with p value being 0.00001. [Table 2]

In IAT score, symptoms in specific (behavior) was categorized into salience, excessive use, neglect work, anticipation, lack of control and neglect social life. These 6 symptoms in specific was measured in mean values and compared between the various categories of students.

Table 3: Symptoms in Specific (Behaviour) according to category of students

Symptoms in Specific	Category of Students				P value
	MBBS students	Post Graduate students	BSC students	Allied science students	
Salience	9.40±4.55	9.0±5.18	8.43±4.54	10.62±8.56	0.11
Excessive use	11.21±4.78	11.53±4.39	7.30±3.93	9.5±5.88	0.00001*
Neglect work	6.03±3.19	5.10±2.58	3.84±2.77	4.75±3.39	0.0001*
Anticipation	3.39±2.10	3.21±1.64	3.56±2.27	3.37±1.96	0.78
Lack of control	7.80±3.38	7.12±3.06	5.25±3.17	7.18±3.74	0.00001*
Neglect social life	1.49±1.94	2.02±2.04	2.05±1.93	2.87±2.60	0.001*

ANOVA test applied

*P<0.05 (Statistically significant)

With regards to salience, though allied science (10.62) and MBBS students (9.4) had slightly higher mean values but this was not significant statistically.

High score for Excessive use was found among post graduate (11.53) and MBBS students (11.21) compared to BSC and allied science students and this difference was found to be statistically significant on ANOVA test with p value being 0.00001. Same trend was found in neglect work group with p value being 0.0001. No statistically

significant difference was found with regards to anticipation scores among the four groups. Highest scores on lack of control were found in MBBS students and least in BSC students and the difference between the four groups was statistically significant (p=0.00001). With regards to neglect social life, highest scores were found in allied science students (2.87) and BSC students (2.05) and least were found in MBBS students (1.49) and this difference between the scores was found to be statistically significant (p=0.001). [Table 3]

Table 4: Comparison of IAT score year wise among different category of Students

Category of Students	Year wise category					P value
	I year	II year	III year	IV year	Internship	
MBBS students	35.02±15.84	36.61±14.93	44.47±12.73	39.29±15.69	39.34±15.56	0.005*
Post Graduate students	40.41±15.06	35.88±15.72	42.37±20.39	--	--	0.57
BSC students	26.88±11.56	34.95±14.0	33.06±16.92	31.15±10.85	--	0.04*
Allied science students	41.06±16.35					--

ANOVA test applied

*P<0.05 (Statistically significant)

Among MBBS students, highest mean IAT score was found in 3rd year (44.47) followed by Internship & 4th year and this difference in mean IAT scores year wise showed a statistically significant difference with p value being 0.005.

No statistically significant difference was observed in mean IAT score among post graduates students though 3rd year PG's had higher mean IAT scores compared to 1st and 2nd years.

Whereas among BSC students, 2nd and 3rd year students had higher mean IAT scores compared to

4th and 1st year students which was statistically significant ($p=0.04$). [Table 4]

Discussion

In the present cross sectional study on Internet addiction among students from a teaching medical college showed that mean age was 21.42 years with female preponderance. These findings were similar to study by Ibrahim AK et al (2022) [10] study, where study participants age ranged from 20 to 25 years with mean age being 21.9 years. But males constituted 45.5% followed by females (49.6%) and 4.9% students did not identify a gender compared to present study which showed a clear female preponderance. This difference could have been due to different geographical and demographic differences.

With regards to severity of IAT score, majority of medical students had mild (45.1%) and moderate (26.1%) respectively; similar results were observed in study by from Mohamed K O et al Sudan (2024) [11] where majority of the medical students had mild (39.7%) and moderate severity (33.2%) of internet addiction. In comparison, study by Subhprada CS et al (2017) found that 52.63% of undergraduate medical students had mild addiction and 24.21% had moderate addiction. None of students in their study reported severe addiction compared to 0.9% in present study. [12] In another study by Acharya S et al (2023) [13] from Nepal also found results in concurrence to the present study; where 47.7% and 27.9% of them had mild and moderate internet addiction respectively.

In contrast to the present study findings, study by Chaudhari et al (2015) [14] found that 41.13% of medical students didn't have internet addiction and 51.42% had mild internet addiction. Only 7.45% of them were moderate addicts and there were no student who is severely addicted to internet. Possible explanation for this variation could be difference in study period where in 2015, the opportunity and availability of Internet was not easy as it is now.

A recent systematic review and meta-analysis on the worldwide prevalence of internet addiction among medical students by Salpynov Z et al (2024) [15] reported that the worldwide prevalence of internet addiction at 29% with higher prevalence in medical students of Southeast Asian region compared to other world regions. Henceforth, public health experts and stake holders should try to find solutions to tackle this public health issue of Internet addiction by taking opinions from the experts and community.

Usually when students join any college, the initial phase of adjustments and opportunity to use internet may be limited compared to when they proceed into further years. With regards to IAT

scores year wise, similar pattern of year wise increase in mean IAT scores among medical graduates was found in a study by Dawadi et al (2022) where compared to 1st and 2nd MBBS students, final year's students had higher IAT scores. [16]

With regards to symptoms in specific (behavior) in present study; excessive use, neglect work, lack of control and neglect social life were statistically significant with category of students indicating the impact of internet addiction.

Present study has assessed the internet addiction and compared it across the four categories of students along with severity. The study didn't consider the factors leading to internet addiction among the students. But since the study was done in a medical college and with reasonably good sample size of 550, the findings of the study reflect the situation of internet addiction among students. Further assessment of mental dimensions and the impact of internet addiction on physical and mental health need to be done. Further the opinions and suggestions from parents and teaching faculty might help us to understand the issue holistically and get relevant solutions.

Conclusions

High prevalence of Internet addiction was found in the present study across all the four categories of students included. A multidisciplinary approach involving students, parents, college faculty, psychiatrists, psychologist and stakeholders opinions and suggestions needs to be considered to tackle this emerging global public health issue and to reduce its impact. Slight lifestyle changes including Yoga and Meditation, encouraging student involvement in sports and regular counseling sessions by experts such as Psychiatrists and Psychologists might help to tackle the issues. Renowned sports personalities, famous personalities and local leader's talks and interactions with students in the college campus will help students to understand the impact of hard work and dedication to reach those heights without being addicted to Internet.

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